

EVALUATION OF THERMAL CYCLING INFLUENCE ON PEI/CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

N.L. Batista¹, K. Iha¹, E.C. Botelho^{2*}

¹ Department of Chemistry, Technological Institute of Aeronautics, São José dos Campos, Brazil, ² Department of Materials, São Paulo State University, Guaratinguetá, Brazil

* Corresponding author (ebotelho@pq.cnpq.br)

Keywords: *PEI, carbon fiber, thermal cycling, reversible stress.*

1 General Introduction

In recent years, high performance thermoplastic composites have been applied in several aircraft parts, such as wings, floor panels, landing gear doors, flaps and radomes, where the long-term properties are of primary importance [1-2]. Among those thermoplastics used in structural applications, there is the polyetherimide (PEI), a high performance amorphous engineering polymer, presenting remarkable mechanical properties even at elevated temperature due to its high glass transition temperature ($T_g \sim 216\text{--}220$ °C), as well as an outstanding fracture resistance into different testing conditions [3].

During service, the effects of environmental exposure on polymer composites and the long-term retention of properties are significant concerns for outdoor applications [4]. The composites are exposed to a variety of climate conditions such as ultraviolet (UV) radiation, humidity and temperature variation, which can alter their mechanical properties [5, 6]. In order to extend the service life of these materials, it is of outmost importance to develop a comprehension of the environmental deterioration [2].

Large and repeated temperature oscillations during an aircraft flight can affect polymeric composite's life [7]. Under thermal cycling, stresses may develop as a consequence of the different coefficient of thermal expansion between the fibers and the matrix, as well as, between the adjacent plies stacked with different orientations in the laminate [7, 8]. In some cases, these stresses can be large enough to damage the material, initiating, for example, matrix microcracking. These microcracks are commonly formed at the interface fiber/matrix and can reduce the strength of the material, as well as act

as sites for environmental degradation and nucleation of macrocracks [8]. Moreover, microcracks can provide a nucleus for further damage types, such as delamination and longitudinal splitting [7].

The purpose of this work is to investigate the effect of thermal cycling on the viscoelastic and mechanical properties of PEI/carbon fiber composites. The influence of the weathering on the material was evaluated by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) test and by determination of tensile and shear modulus from resonant frequencies.

2 Material and Methods

2.1 Materials

The PEI/carbon fiber composite plates, supplied by Ten Cate Advanced Composite Materials Company, consisted of eight plies of carbon fiber fabric reinforcements ($0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ$) with 5 Hardness Satin textile style (5HS) and 50% of carbon fiber in volume.

2.2 Thermal shock weathering

Thermal cycling weathering was carried out on an Envirotronics two zone vertical thermal shock test chamber, Model TSV 5-2-2-2-AC. In order to simulate a flight envelop of an airplane, the composite was exposed to several cycles of 10 minutes at -50°C followed by 10 minutes at $+80^\circ\text{C}$. The thermal cycling was performed for 1000 and 2000 cycles.

2.3 Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMA)

Dynamic mechanical thermal analyses (DMA) were conducted in a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer from Seiko SII Exstar 6000 using a temperature range of

30 to 250 °C at a heating rate of 3 °C/min over a frequency of 1 Hz and a maximum displacement of 10 µm. These analyses were performed using a dual cantilever bending mode with dimensions of 50mm x 10mm x 2.5mm.

2.4 Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS)

Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) tests were carried out on a Shimadzu Precision Universal Tester (Autograph AG-X Series), at constant cross-speed of 1.3 mm/min. According to ASTM D2344 standard, five specimens with dimensions of 15 mm x 6 mm x 2.5 mm were used.

2.5 Determination of Young's and shear moduli

The impulse excitation technique was applied using a Sonelastic® equipment, developed by ATCP – Physical Engineering at Brazil, to determinate Young's and shear moduli from the natural frequency. At the technique applied, a rectangular specimen is lightly stroked with an electromagnetic impulse and the Young's and shear moduli are calculated from the natural frequencies of vibration, under flexure and torsion modes, respectively. Those values depend only on the dimensions and weight of specimen.

The Young's modulus can be calculated from the material's natural frequency in flexure mode by using the following relationship:

$$E = 0.9465 \left(\frac{mf_f^2}{b} \right) \left(\frac{L^3}{t^3} \right)$$

where m is the weight of the specimen, f_f is the natural frequency of the bar under flexural loading, and b, L, and t are the width, length, and thickness of the bar, respectively. T can be obtained from:

$$T = 1 + 6.858 \left(\frac{t}{L} \right)^2$$

The shear modulus can be calculated from the material's natural frequency in torsion mode by using the following equation:

$$G = \frac{4Lmf_t^2}{bt} \left(\frac{B}{1+A} \right)$$

where f_t is the frequency of the bar under torsion mode. A and B parameters can be calculated by:

$$B = \left(\frac{b/t + t/b}{4(t/b) - 2.52(t/b)^2 + 0.21(t/b)^6} \right)$$

$$A = \left(\frac{0.5062 - 0.8776(b/t) + 0.3504(b/t)^2 - 0.0078(b/t)^3}{12.03(b/t) + 9.892(b/t)^2} \right)$$

This non destructive test was conducted using specimens with dimension of 100 mm x 20 mm x 2.5 mm, according to ASTM 1876 standard.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMA)

The thermal shock effects on the viscoelastic behavior of PEI/carbon fiber composite is presented in Figure 1(a-c).

Figure 1. DMA results variation during thermal cycling.

The glass transition temperatures (T_g), taken from the onset of the storage modulus curves (Figure 1(a)), didn't show a significant change during weathering. However, the specimens exposed to 1000 cycles presented a small reduction of approximately 5% on the storage modulus. While no reduction was found on the storage modulus of specimens exposed up to 2000 cycles, indicating that microcracking formation is not likely.

The loss modulus curves obtained (Figure 1(b)) show that the thermal cycling didn't promote a significant increase in the loss moduli values in the course of weathering. Tan δ curves also did not present a significant change, as observed in Figure 1(c). Thus, no physical damage could be identified on composites matrix or interface after the thermal cycling.

The ILSS values of PEI/carbon fiber composites, during the thermal cycling, are presented in Figure 2. As it can be observed, no significant variations of the ILSS results can be found after the thermal cycling weathering, in agreement with the DMA results. Despite the fact that the specimens cycled 1000 times presented a small decrease on the ILSS values, the specimens cycled 2000 times showed a small increase on those values, which suggests that thermal cycling was not severe enough to form microcracks and promote degradation at fiber/matrix interface.

Figure 2. Thermal cycling effect on ILSS values.

Figure 3 shows the dynamic Young's and shear moduli of PEI/carbon fiber composites during thermal cycling. As it can be seen, after 1000 cycles there was a small reduction on Young's and shear moduli (1.9% and 1.1%, respectively). However, after 2000 thermal cycles, the shear modulus suffered a substantial reduction (16.5%), while Young's modulus suffered a recovery.

Figure 3. Thermal cycling effect on Young's and shear moduli.

On previous works, similar recoveries, as found for Young's modulus, have been related for various materials [9-13]. Comparing the Young's modulus result, obtained from the impulse excitation technique, with DMA and ILSS results, it can be verified that all of them showed a reduction of the strength values after 1000 thermal cycles followed by a recovery, after being exposed to 2000 thermal cycles. Nevertheless, at all the tests considered, the specimens were evaluated in the longitudinal direction, different from the shear modulus obtained from the torsion mode, which was evaluated at the transversal direction. Thus, the DMA and ILSS results are according with the Young's modulus results.

A work on porosity reduction in composites [13] concluded that the reduction of porosity on a laminate with fibers oriented at 0° (longitudinal direction) increased the Young's modulus, while a reduction on porosity on a laminate oriented at 45° (transversal direction) increased the shear modulus. A similar behavior was found for the thermal cycled specimens; however, in the last case the strength variation is not related with the reinforcement orientation, but with the direction of a reversible stress formation.

In addition, a study made previously, with metallic composites [14], related their results presenting a strength alternation with a reversible stress accommodation on the interfacial region, controlled by a friction mechanism. Even though the mechanisms involved in metallic composites are quite different from those related to the polymeric composites; the direction oscillation of the most affected region by thermal cycling, longitudinal or transversal, was probably due to a reversible stress formation.

The strength recovery observed after 2000 cycles for DMA, ILSS and Young's modulus, thus as the inversion verified in shear modulus, corroborates that microcracking formation is not likely. The orientation variation of the most affected region by thermal cycling, longitudinal or transversal loadings, was probably due to a reversible stress formation.

4 Conclusions

Thermal cycling induced the formation of reversible stresses at fiber/matrix interface, affecting the longitudinal or transversal region. At 1000 thermal cycles, the storage modulus, ILSS and Young's modulus values decreased. On the other hand, after 2000 thermal cycles, only the shear modulus of the composite was reduced. In the last case, although the reduction was severe, the results indicate no microcracking formation.

References

- [1] E. C. Botelho and M. C. Rezende "Evaluation by Free Vibration Method of Moisture Absorption Effects in Polyamide/Carbon Fiber Laminates". *J Thermoplast Compos*, Vol.23, No. 2, pp 207-225, 2010.
- [2] T. Yilma and T. Sinmazcelik "Effects of hydrothermal aging on glass-fiber/polyetherimide (PEI) composites". *J Mater Sci*, Vol. 45, No. 2, pp 399-404, 2010.
- [3] S. Kumar, T. Rath, R. N. Mahaling, et al. "Study on mechanical, morphological and electrical properties of carbon nanofiber/polyetherimide composites". *Mater Sci Eng B*, Vol. 141, No. 1-2, pp 61-70, 2007.
- [4] Y. I. Tsai, E. J. Bosze, E. Barjasteh, et al. "Influence of hygrothermal environment on thermal and mechanical properties of carbon fiber/fiberglass hybrid composites". *Compos Sci Technol*, Vol. 69, No. 3, pp 432-437, 2009.
- [5] V. S. Chevali, D. R. Dean and G. M. Janowski "Effect of environmental weathering on flexural creep behavior of long fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites". *Polym Degrad Stabil*, Vol. 95, No. 12, pp 2628-2640, 2010.
- [6] B. P. Jelle and T. N. Nilsen "Comparison of accelerated climate ageing methods of polymer building materials by attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared radiation spectroscopy". *Constr Build Mater*, Vol. 25, No. 3, pp 2122-2132, 2011.

- [7] G. C. Papanicolaou, A. G. Xepapadaki and G. D. Tagaris “Effect of thermal shock cycling on the creep behavior of glass-epoxy composites”. *Compos Struct*, Vol. 88, No. 3, pp 436-442, 2009.
- [8] M. S. Kumar, N. Sharma and B. C. Ray “Microstructural and Mechanical Aspects of Carbon/Epoxy Composites at Liquid Nitrogen Temperature”. *J Reinf Plast Comp*, Vol. 28, No. 16, pp 2013-2023, 2009.
- [9] N. Chawla, K. K. Chawla, M. Koopman, et al. “Thermal-shock behavior of a Nicalon-fiber-reinforced hybrid glass-ceramic composite”. *Compos Sci Technol*, Vol. 61, pp 1923–1930, 2001.
- [10] A. H. A. Pereira, G. M. Fortes, B. Schickle, et al. “Correlation between changes in mechanical strength and damping of a high alumina refractory castable progressively damaged by thermal shock”. *Cerâmica*, Vol.56, No. 336, pp 311-314, 2010.
- [11] N. L. Hancox “Thermal effects on polymer matrix composites: Part 1. Thermal cycling”. *Mater Design*, Vol. 19, No 3, pp 85-91, 1998.
- [12] F. Kawano, T. Ohguri, T. Ichikawa, et al. “Influence of thermal cycles in water on flexural strength of laboratory-processed composite resin”. *J Oral Rehabil*, Vol. 28, No. 9, pp 703-707, 2001.
- [13] M. Cerný, P. Glogar and L. M. Manocha “Resonant frequency study of tensile and shear elasticity moduli of carbon fibre reinforced composites (CFRC)”. *Carbon*, Vol. 38, No. 15, pp 2139–2149, 2000.
- [14] R. Schaller “Metal matrix composites, a smart choice for high damping materials”. *J Alloy Compd*, Vol. 355, No. 1, pp 131–135, 2003.

Figure 1(a)

Figure 1(b)

Figure 1(c)

Figure 2

Figure 3